

An overview on 'Chiron' approach to total synthesis of biologically active natural products from our laboratory[†]

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Manuscript received 18 July 2013, accepted 19 July 2013

Introduction

'Chiron' approach synthesis is a method of synthesis which utilizes the stereochemistry of the starting material as chiral pool for the synthesis of functionally and stereochemically complex natural products and natural product-like molecules^{1,2}. Chiral pool materials can be derived from carbohydrates, amino acids, organic acids, terpenes, etc. Since long we know that carbohydrates are rich source of energy for metabolic processes that are going on in the living system. The mono- and oligosaccharide units of carbohydrates are carrier for information in many recognition processes at the molecular level. Carbohydrate-based building blocks (CBBs), the terminology given by Alessandro Dondoni³, are very cost-effective if they are derived from inexpensive sugars. Apart from that, commercially available carbohydrates are being utilized by synthetic organic chemists as versatile CBBs for the synthesis of various types of chiral molecules.

Natural products have played a key role in drug discovery and development process by providing various novel biological active molecules exhibiting anticancer, antiprotozoal, antifeedant, anathematic, antiepileptic and antimicrobial activities. Some of them have seen great success as clinically useful medicines⁴. It has been seen during the last few years that cancer is now the most frequent causative disease of deaths and has got the first place⁵ in the developed countries (specially in the United States). Quite a good number of natural products especially having anticancer activity have been identified during recent years. These naturally occurring anticancer molecules have aroused immense interest among the chem-

ists to develop them or their various analogues as powerful synthetic drugs. American Chemical Society released a data in 2009 showing that more than 14,79,350 new cases of cancer (all types, excluding basal and squamous cell skin cancers) are detected each year in the United States alone, that led to 40,000 deaths and the same trend can be observed for developing countries also. So there is a pressing need for safe and effective antitumor agent to control cancer.

The marine ecosystem is a vast and virtually unexplored extraordinary reservoir for the discovery of structurally diverse natural products⁶. Recently several novel compounds have been isolated from numerous marine organisms, including algae, molluscs, corals, sponges, tunicates and phytoplankton and their importance has been recognized after evaluating them for their startling biological activities that include potent cytotoxic, immunosuppressive and antibiotic properties. However, the low natural abundance of these molecules of marine origin makes them financially prohibitive to develop as drugs. To overcome this problem, economically viable and practical synthetic routes are essentially required, thus offering compelling challenges to the synthetic organic chemistry community to provide a sustainable amount of the material to further investigate their biological profiles.

My group is actively involved towards the syntheses of natural products and natural product-inspired molecules of biological significance under CSIR-CDRI drug development programme. Herein, I have discussed in brief the syntheses of few biologically active marine natural prod-

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

ucts reported by our group starting from commercially available chiral pool materials (chiral building blocks).

Stereoselective synthesis of jaspine B⁷

Jaspine B (anhydrophytosphingosine) was first isolated from the Okinawan marine sponge *Pachastrissa* sp. by Higa and co-workers in 2002 and found to possess cytotoxicity at a level of IC₅₀ 0.01 µg/mL against P388, A549, HT29 and MeL28 cell lines⁸. In the year 2003, Debitus and co-workers isolated the same natural product from a different sponge, *Jaspis* sp., and named it as jaspine B⁹. Preliminary bioassay studies conducted by Du *et al.* showed that jaspine B exhibited strong inhibition activities against human MDA231, Hela and CNE cell lines¹⁰, indicating potential usage in various cancer treatments. Moreover, the structural simplicity of this natural product coupled with its biological activity sparked great interest in the synthetic chemists' community, which, to date, has culminated in several approaches to the synthesis of jaspine B^{11–23}. Syntheses of truncated analogues have also been reported based upon manipulation of L-xylose²⁴ and 4-(benzyloxy)-but-2-ene-1-ol²⁵, respectively. A review on the synthesis and structural assignment of jaspine B and 2-*epi*-jaspine B was published by Davies *et al.*²⁶.

The basic requirements for cost-effective and efficient synthesis are the choice of a proper starting material that requires minimal protection-deprotection manipulations, a high level of stereocontrol and less purification steps. Keeping this point in mind, we realized the synthesis of jaspine B by envisaging its retrosynthetic analysis, as shown in Fig. 1. Our method for the stereoselective synthesis of jaspine B involved 8 steps starting from a most versatile starting material, 3,4,6-tri-*O*-benzyl-D-galactal,

which can be easily synthesized in laboratory on a multi-gram scale from D-galactose.

We took the advantage of our previously developed methodology^{27a} for constructing the THF moiety in jaspine B. The synthesis of trisubstituted THF **4** was possible by intramolecular asymmetric ring opening (ARO) of a stereochemically pure epoxide-derived from allylic alcohol **3** under Sharpless asymmetric epoxidation conditions and by some additional protecting group manipulations. The progenitor **4** can be easily obtained from commercially available 3,4,6-tri-*O*-benzyl-D-galactal by involving its three-steps chemical transformations as shown in Scheme 1. First, the D-galactal was subjected to Perlin hydrolysis^{27b} to provide α,β-unsaturated aldehyde **2** which on Luche reduction furnished enantiopure allylic alcohol **3** whose intramolecular asymmetric ring opening (ARO) reaction under Sharpless asymmetric epoxidation conditions delivered the required THF **4**.

In our synthetic protocol the THF domain **4**^{27a}, the key intermediate with well defined chiral centers, was transformed to azido derivative **6**. Its sequential hydrolysis-oxidation-Wittig olefination (SHOWO)²⁸, gave a mixture of *E* and *Z* olefins **8** which had three contiguous chiral centers with the same stereochemistries as present in jaspine B. Finally, the hydrogenation of **8** furnished the target molecule (Scheme 2).

Total synthesis of a new antiepileptic ceramide²⁹

Ceramides are a family of lipid molecules consisting of a sphingosine linked to a fatty acid via an amide bond (Fig. 2)³⁰. They are found in high concentrations within the cell membrane of cells as they are one of the lipid components that make up sphingomyelin, one of the ma-

Fig. 1

Scheme 1. Stereoselective synthesis of THF domain : Reagents and conditions : (i) HgSO₄ (cat.), 0.01 N H₂SO₄, 1,4-dioxane, 0 °C→rt, 8 h; (ii) NaBH₄ (0.5 equiv.), CeCl₃·7H₂O (1.0 equiv.), EtOH, 0 °C→rt, 3 h, 65% for 2 steps; (iii) Ti(Oi-Pr)₄ (1.0 equiv.), L-(+)-DET (1.2 equiv.), *t*-BuOOH (2.0 equiv.), MS 4 Å, CH₂Cl₂, -25 °C→0 °C, 2.5 h, sat. citric acid in acetone, 2 h, 48%.

Scheme 2. Stereoselective synthesis of jaspine B (**9**) : Reagents and conditions : (i) MsCl, Et₃N, CH₂Cl₂, 0 °C→rt, 1.5 h; (ii) NaN₃, Bu₄NCl (cat.), DMF, 120 °C, 3 days, 62% for 2 steps; (iii) H₅IO₆ (1.3 equiv.), EtOAc, 3 h; (iv) C₁₃H₂₇PPh₃⁺ Br⁻, *n*-BuLi, dry THF, -78 °C, Ar, 82% for 2 steps; (v) HCO₂NH₄, MeOH, Pd/C, reflux, 18 h, 72%.

lor lipids in the lipid bilayer. For years, ceramides and other sphingolipids found in the bilayer cell membrane were assumed as purely structural elements but now this is known to be not completely true.

When the substituent (R) in this structure is H, the resulting molecule is a ceramide

Fig. 2. General chemical structure of sphingolipid.

Recent evidence suggests that ceramide can actually act as a signaling molecule. The most well-known functions of ceramides as cellular signals include apoptosis, cell growth arrest, differentiation, cell senescence, cell migration and adhesion. Furthermore, ceramides have also been suggested in a number of pathological states including cancer, neurodegeneration, diabetes, microbial pathogenesis, obesity and inflammation³¹.

A new ceramide mixture **22** having two ceramides **22a** and **22b** was isolated from *Negombata corticata*, a red sea sponge by Ahmed and co-workers in 2008 (Fig. 3)³². This mixture was found to exhibit *in vivo* anticonvulsant^{33a} activity comparable to diazepam^{33b}.

Fig. 3. Structure of the antiepileptic ceramides mixture (**22a** and **22b**).

Epilepsy, a seizure disorder, affects the nervous system and is characterized by 40 different types of recur-

rent unprovoked seizures³⁴. As per the report of WHO, around 50 million population of world is affected by epilepsy, out of which 90% are found in developing countries^{35a}. The current marketed drugs that provide ample seizure control in many patients have notable side effects and about 28 to 30% patients are not fully cured (seizure-free) with the available antiepileptic drugs^{35b}. The available medicines cannot fully control epilepsy and that's why there is a continuing need for safe and more effective antiepileptic agents to control epilepsy.

Motivated by the biological activities associated with ceramides and the antiepileptic activity of the ceramide mixture **22** and also as a result of our interest towards the total synthesis of biologically important natural products and their analogues, we developed an efficient approach for the total synthesis of antiepileptic ceramide **22b** starting from commercially available sugars³⁶. The retrosynthetic strategy for target ceramide **22b** is depicted in Scheme 3.

Here we envisaged that 3,4,6-tri-*O*-benzyl-D-galactal **1** was the choice of chiral building block for the synthesis of target molecule. Its exposure to 4 *M* H₂SO₄ in THF furnished 2-deoxy-D-galactose **10**³⁷ whose Wittig methylenation³⁸ gave the alcohol **11**. Several attempts were taken to optimize Wittig methylenation of hemiacetal **10** and gratifyingly, performing the reaction at -25 °C furnished **11** in 82% yield (Scheme 4).

The next step was to complete the synthesis of compound **13**, which required S_N2 displacement of OH at C-2 in compound **11** with a nitrogen nucleophile under Mitsunobu condition in presence of PPh₃, diphenylphosphoryl azide (DPPA) and diisopropyl azidodicarboxylate (DIAD) in THF at -20 °C to 0 °C^{38a}. Unfortunately, the stereochemical inversion was futile when **11** was subjected to Mitsunobu reaction. Another attempt to derivatize the free OH in **11** to 2-*O*-mesylate, followed by its S_N2 displacement with sodium azide in DMF was also dis-

Scheme 3. Retrosynthetic analysis of ceramide **22b**.

appointing and yielded a complex mixture of products. Similarly, S_N2 displacement of its 2-*O*-triflate derivative with sodium azide at 0 °C to room temperature was also unsuccessful.

Scheme 4. Reagents and conditions : (a) 4 M H₂SO₄, THF, 0 °C to rt, 12 h, quantitative; (b) Ph₃PCH₂Br, *n*-BuLi, THF, -25 °C, 3 h, 82%.

Gratifyingly, when the alcohol **11** was subjected to undergo inversion under Mitsunobu condition in presence of PPh₃, phthalimide and DIAD in THF at -20 °C to room temperature, the desired inverted phthalimido compound **12** was obtained in 75% yield (Scheme 5)^{38b,39,40}. In the next step it was treated with MeNH₂ in EtOH-H₂O (1 : 1) for 2 days at room temperature to obtain the corresponding amine⁴¹. The crude amine after passing through a short column of silica gel was acylated⁴² by treating it with stearoyl chloride in the presence of aqueous K₂CO₃ to obtain **13** with the natural ceramide backbone in 77% yield over two steps (Scheme 5).

Our next attempt was focused on synthesis of long chain olefin counterpart **20**. Its straightforward synthesis from commercially available 1,12-dodecanediol is shown

in Scheme 6. It was protected with TBSCl to 12-(*tert*-butyldimethylsilyloxy)dodecan-1-ol **14**⁴³, followed by its oxidation with IBX (2-iodoxybenzoic acid) to obtain aldehyde **15** which on Wittig olefination furnished olefin **16** in 81% yield over two steps. The olefin **17**, obtained in excellent yield (92%) after the cleavage of silyl ether with TBAF, was then hydrogenated in the presence of Pd/C to obtain the saturated alcohol **18** which on oxidation with IBX, followed by Wittig olefination of the resulting aldehyde **19** furnished the desired long chain olefin **20** in 89% yield over three steps (Scheme 6).

The above described building blocks **13** and **20** were now coupled together in the next step by cross metathesis in the presence of Grubbs 2nd generation catalyst (5 mol%) to obtain **21**⁴⁴, a synthetic precursor of ceramide **22b** (Scheme 7)²⁹. At this stage it was observed that by increasing the equivalents of long chain alkene **20**, the yield of the cross metathesis product was enhanced^{36a,b}. Thus, when 3 equivalents of alkene **20** were used, the cross metathesis product **21** was obtained in 79% yield.

Unfortunately, the removal of double bond and benzyl protection in **21** under an atmosphere of H₂ in the presence of catalytic amount of 10% Pd/C or Pd(OH)₂ by dissolving it in different solvent systems afforded the desired product **22b** with very low yield and it was presumably due to the problem associated with poor solubility of the corresponding intermediates and the target ceramide

Scheme 5. Reagents and conditions : (a) PPh₃, DIAD, phthalimide, THF, -20 °C to rt, overnight, 75%; (b) MeNH₂, EtOH-H₂O (1 : 1), 48 h, rt; (c) C₁₇H₃₅COCl, aqueous K₂CO₃, DCM, 0 °C to rt, 2 h, 77% from **12**.

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Scheme 6. Reagents and conditions : (a) TBDMSCl, NaH, THF, 12 h, 55%; (b) IBX, CH₃CN, reflux, 1 h; (c) *i*-PrCH₂CH₂PPh₃Br, *t*-BuOK, THF, -20 °C to rt, 3 h, 81% for 2 steps; (d) TBAF, THF, 0 °C to rt, 2 h, 92%; (e) H₂/Pd-C, EtOH, rt, 12 h; (f) IBX, CH₃CN, reflux, 1 h; (g) Ph₃P=CH₂, THF, -20 °C to rt, 2 h, 89% for 3 steps.

Scheme 7. Synthesis of ceramides **22b** and **23**. Reagents and conditions : (a) Grubbs 2nd gen. catalyst, DCM, reflux, 6 h, 79%; (b) H₂/Pd-C, MeOH : CHCl₃ : AcOH (5 : 3 : 2), rt, 10 h; (c) Ac₂O, pyridine, DMAP, 0 °C to rt, 12 h, 52% over two steps.

formed during hydrogenation. However, hydrogenation of **21** in MeOH : CHCl₃ : AcOH (5 : 3 : 2) in the presence of 10% Pd/C by adopting the method reported by Lee *et al.* proceeded smoothly to provide the target natural product **22b**⁴⁵. The chromatographic purification of the reaction mixture with MeOH/CHCl₃ (1/5, v/v) furnished **22b** in 28% yield. Here, it is worth noting that most of the hydrogenated product got stuck in the column during column chromatography (silica gel) owing to the highly polar nature of the ceramide **22b** and thus the isolated yield of **22b** was low.

¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of ceramide mixture **22** (**22a** and **22b**) in CHCl₃ as well as in C₅D₅N was reported by Ahmed *et al.*³². Our synthesized, chromatographically pure ceramide **22b** was insoluble both in CHCl₃ and MeOH. Hence, the ¹H NMR of **22b** was recorded in a (2 : 1) mixture of CDCl₃ and CD₃OD. However, its ¹³C NMR spectrum could not be recorded due to poor solubility. In order to confirm its structure completely, the precursor **21** was hydrogenated with H₂ in presence of 10% Pd/C and the resulting crude product mixture was acetylated with Ac₂O and pyridine in the presence of catalytic amount of DMAP to its corresponding triacetyl derivative **23** in 52% yield over two steps from **21** (Scheme 7). The complete identification of the triacetyl derivative **23** by analyzing its detailed spectral data finally led to the

unambiguous confirmation of the formation of the target trihydroxy natural ceramide **22b**.

First total synthesis of (+)-varitriol⁴⁶

In last decades, marine microorganisms have being recognized as important sources of pharmacologically active metabolites due to the need for compounds possessing biological activity and other economically useful properties such as fine chemicals, drugs, cosmetics and functional personal-care products⁴⁷. In particular, a growing number of marine-derived fungi have been reported to produce novel bioactive secondary metabolites⁴⁸. To this end, a variety of species have been screened for their biological activity and a variety of bioactive molecules, often with toxic properties and unique structural features, have been isolated. The rapid growth in the chemistry of marine organisms over the last five decades has led to the discovery of a surprisingly large number of novel structures. More than fifteen compounds from marine source are currently in human clinical trials⁴⁹.

In 2002, Barrero and co-workers reported the isolation and structure elucidation of (+)-varitriol (**43**) from M75-2 marine strain of the fungus *Emericella varicolor*, isolated from a sponge collected in Venezuelan waters of the Caribbean Sea (Fig. 4)⁵⁰. This substance exhibited potent cytotoxicities towards a variety of cancer cell lines. Strikingly, (+)-varitriol demonstrated a more than 100-

Fig. 4

fold increased potency (over the mean toxicity) toward the RXF 393 (renal cancer, $GI_{50} = 1.63 \times 10^{-7} M$) T-47D (breast cancer, $GI_{50} = 2.10 \times 10^{-7} M$) and SNB-75 (CNS cancer, $GI_{50} = 2.44 \times 10^{-7} M$) cell lines and lower potency against the DU-145 (prostate cancer, $GI_{50} = 1.10 \times 10^{-6} M$), HL-60 (TB) (leukemia, $GI_{50} = 2.52 \times 10^{-5} M$), CCRFCM (leukemia, $GI_{50} = 2.60 \times 10^{-5} M$), OVCAR-5 (ovarian cancer, $GI_{50} = 6.82 \times 10^{-5} M$), SNB-19 (CNS cancer, $GI_{50} = 9.13 \times 10^{-5} M$) and COLO 205 (colon cancer, $GI_{50} = 9.59 \times 10^{-5} M$) cell lines when tested within the 60 cell line panel of the National Cancer Institute (NCI), although its mode of action is still unknown⁵¹. This array of interesting biological properties has attracted an immense synthetic interest directed towards (+)-varitriol and their analogues.

Clemens *et al.*⁵² and subsequently the Taylor group⁵³ have disclosed the total synthesis of unnatural (-)-varitriol. Both groups utilized D-(-)-ribose to construct the furanose portion of (-)-varitriol and argued that the synthesis of the natural isomer might be possible from the expensive L-(+)-ribose. Since L-(+)-ribose is highly expensive (it costs Rs. 3,26,500/- per 25 g) we were looking for cheaper starting material for our work on total synthesis of (+)-varitriol (**43**).

Our group disclosed the first total synthesis of (+)-varitriol (**43**) from methyl α ,D-mannopyranoside **24** (it costs Rs. 1,897 per 25 g)⁴⁶. We envisaged from retrosynthetic analysis of **43**, delineated in Scheme 8, that it could be elaborated by the coupling of aromatic and carbohydrate portions **41** and **34**, respectively by utilizing the cross metathesis strategy. The fragment **34**, containing all the four required stereocenters of **43**, could be prepared from the key tetrahydrofuran (THF) intermediate **27** by reducing the iodide at C6 with $LiAlH_4$, followed by the inversion of configuration at C4 and Wittig

olefination at C2'. The THF **27** could be derived from the methyl α ,D-mannopyranoside **24**. Aromatic part **41** could be obtained from the triflate **37**^{54,55} by Stille coupling. The retrosynthetic strategy is summarized in Scheme 8.

Scheme 8. Retrosynthetic strategy.

Fig. 5

Our synthesis for the title molecule was initiated with commercially available methyl α ,D-mannopyranoside **24** which was much cheaper than L-(+)-ribose. The entire synthetic strategy to obtain the required THF counterpart of (+)-varitriol (**43**) is delineated in Scheme 9. The zinc dust-mediated opening⁵⁶ of methyl 6-deoxy-6-iodo-2,3-di-O-benzyl- α ,D-mannopyranoside **25**^{57a,b}, followed by sodium borohydride reduction of the resulting aldehyde furnished the allylic alcohol **26**. Its iodocyclization involving the participation of secondary benzyl protected oxygen furnished 4,5-*cis* tetra substituted THF **27** with very high diastereoselectivity ($>99 : 1$)^{57a,c-e}. The high

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Scheme 9. Reagents and conditions : (a) Ref. 57; (b) (i) Zn dust, NH_4Cl , cyanocobalamin, MeOH, rt, 30 min, (ii) NaBH_4 , MeOH, 0 °C, 3 h, 60% from **25**; (c) I_2 , DCM, 0 °C, 2 h, 78%; (d) (i) LiAlH_4 , THF, -78 to 0 °C, 3 h; (ii) TBDPSCI, pyridine, 12 h, 85% from **27**; (e) (i) Dess-Martin periodinane, DCM, 2 h, 0 °C to rt; (ii) L-selectride, THF, -78 °C, 3 h, 90% from **28**; (f) (i) $\text{Pd}(\text{OH})_2$, H_2 , MeOH, rt, 12 h, (ii) 2,2-DMP, acetone, CSA, rt, 6 h, 86% from **29**; (g) 80% AcOH, 80 °C, 2 h, 94%; (h) PMBCl , NaH, TBAI, DMF, 0 °C to rt, 2 h, 54%; (i) TBAF, THF, 0 °C to rt, 1 h, 95%; (j) IBX, CH_3CN , 80 °C, 1 h; (k) $\text{Ph}_3\text{PCH}_2\text{Br}$, KHMDS, THF, -78 °C to rt, 1 h, 77% from **33**.

selectivity was attributed to I_2/π -complex formation at *re* face of the double bond in most favorable acyclic conformation⁵⁸ of alcohol **26a**. The *si* face approach of the I_2 across the double bond is unfavorable due to the bulky benzyloxy group (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6

Among the four stereocenters in α -C-furanoside **28** which were derived from **27** after its LAH reduction, except C4, three of them had the required stereochemistry as present in the (+)-varitriol while C-4 had the opposite stereochemistry. Here, the inversion of C4-OH group was done to provide the isomeric compound **29** by oxidizing its precursor **28**, followed by the reduction of the resulting crude ketone with different hydride reagents. The best result in terms of selectivity (>99 : 1) and yield (90%) was observed when L-selectride was used as the reducing agent. The *syn* stereochemistries of C2, C5 and C3, C4 of the furanoside **29** were confirmed by NOESY spectrum of its acetonide derivative **30**.

In the next step, we faced a problem during the oxidation of compound **30a** by IBX in acetonitrile⁵⁹ to obtain

the corresponding aldehyde due to its high volatile nature⁵². However, aldehyde **33a** was obtained when the primary OH group in compound **33**, whose molecular weight was higher than that of **30** due to PMB ether protections of its both the secondary OH groups, was oxidized with IBX in CH_3CN at 80 °C. Its Wittig olefination furnished the olefin **34** and that was ready for cross metathesis with the aromatic olefin **41** to give the PMB protected (+)-varitriol.

Our next attempt was focused on straight forward construction of aromatic portion **41**, as in shown in Scheme 10. The commercially available phenolic acid **35** was utilized as the starting material to synthesize the required olefin **41**. The key step was Stille coupling of tributylvinyl tin (TBVT) with the triflate **37**^{54,55} in the presence of tetrakis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(0) and lithium chloride in a sealed tube⁶⁰ at 80 °C to afford compound **38**. Its LiAlH_4 reduction, followed by methylation of phenolic OH and subsequently silyl protection of primary alcohol, furnished **41**.

The two building blocks **34** and **41** were coupled together in the next step in the presence of Grubbs 2nd generation catalyst⁶¹ (5 mol%) to obtain the fully protected natural product analogue **42**. Our attempt to remove the PMB ethers of **42** by adopting standard procedures (DDQ, 10%–5%, 2% TFA/DCM) was futile. However, to our delight, prolonged exposure of **42** to 1 M HCl in THF at room temperature (~35 °C) for 3 days delivered the natural product (+)-varitriol **43** in 46% yield (Scheme 11).

As I have discussed above, chiral pool materials can

Scheme 10. Reagents and conditions : (a) Ref. 54; (b) Ref. 55; (c) tributylvinyl tin, Pd(PPh₃)₄, LiCl, THF, sealed tube, 80 °C, 30 h, 94%; (d) LiAlH₄, THF, 0 °C to rt, 2 h, 72%; (e) MeI, K₂CO₃, acetone, reflux, 5 h, 88%; (f) TBSCl, imidazole, DCM, rt, 1 h, 93%.

Scheme 11. Reagents and conditions : (a) Grubbs 2nd generation catalyst, DCM, reflux, 12 h, 51%; (b) 1 M HCl, THF, rt, 3 days, 46%.

also be derived from natural chiral amino acids apart from carbohydrates and are considered to be useful tools in total synthesis. My group is also utilizing natural amino acids for the syntheses of various types of natural products and natural product-like molecules. Few years back we reported the stereoselective synthesis of (+)-spisulosine, an anticancer molecule, starting from naturally occurring L-serine. A brief discussion on its synthesis is given below.

Total synthesis of anticancer agent (+)-spisulosine (ES-285)⁶²

The role of natural products in anticancer drug discovery is very impressive. It has been observed that about 75% of all drugs, now in clinical trial for cancer therapy, are either natural products or pharmacophores obtained from natural products⁶³. Spisulosine **52** or ES-285 ((2*S*,3*R*)-2-amino-3-octanedecanol) (Fig. 7) is a marine bioactive compound which was isolated by Reinhart *et al.*⁶⁴ from the North Arctic clam *Spisula polynyma*. It is a sphingoid-type base containing a long saturated C₁₈ alkyl chain and *erythro*-1,2-amino alcohol and was found to exhibit potent cytotoxicity and morphological alteration against L1210 leukemia cells. Its *in vitro* activity

Figure 7. Structure of (+)-spisulosine or ES-285 (**52**).

was also screened against P-388 (0.01 µg/ml), HT-29 (0.05 µg/ml) and MEL-28 (0.05 µg/ml) tumor cell lines⁶⁴.

Due to the potent antiproliferative activity⁶⁵ of (+)-spisulosine towards advanced malignant solid tumors⁶⁶, it has been included in clinical trial as a potential antitumoral agent. Owing to its simple structure and potent biological activity, it has garnered much attention from the synthetic community. Several approaches for its synthesis have been disclosed. The first total synthesis of (+)-spisulosine was disclosed from L-alanine methyl ester hydrochloride⁶⁴. Later its formal synthesis was achieved by Lee *et al.* from chiral 2-aziridine carboxylate⁶⁷. Allepuz *et al.* completed its asymmetric synthesis from the *N*-benzylimine derived from D-mannitol⁶⁸. Later, the total synthesis of the title natural product from enantiopure *N*-*tert*-butylsulfinyl imine was reported by Séguin *et al.*⁶⁹. Coelho *et al.* published the total synthesis of (±)-spisulosine starting from hexadecanal involving Morita-Baylis-Hillman (MBH) chemistry⁷⁰. Our ongoing programme on 'chiron' approach to total synthesis of bioactive natural products and their analogues stimulated us to explore a convenient approach to the synthesis of this interesting natural product⁷¹.

We completed the total synthesis of the title molecule starting from easily available L-serine-derived (*S*)-Garner's aldehyde **44** (Scheme 12)⁷². The synthetic strategy involved the introduction of hydroxy group at C3 of the natural product by highly diastereoselective nucleophilic addition on Garner's aldehyde, resulting in a mixture of

Scheme 12. Synthesis of (+)-spisulosine (**52**). Reagents and conditions : (a) vinyl magnesium bromide, THF, $-78\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 74%; (b) benzyl bromide, NaH, DMF, 91%; (c) PTSA, MeOH, $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 84%; (d) TsCl, Et_3N , DCM, $25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 73%; (e) LiAlH_4 , THF, $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 80%; (f) Grubbs 2nd generation catalyst (5 mol%), 1-pentadecene, DCM, reflux, 87%; (g) H_2 , Pd/C, MeOH- CHCl_3 , 91%; (h) (i) HCl-dioxane, rt, (ii) aq. NaOH, DCM, rt, 90%.

anti and *syn* terminal alkenic alcohols in 6 : 1 ratio^{73a,b}. The major *anti* isomer **45** was separated from this mixture by column chromatography. Its benzyl ether derivative **46** was subjected to smooth isopropylidene opening with PTSA in MeOH at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to obtain the intermediate **47**. Its free hydroxymethyl group at C1 was converted into methyl group to obtain the assembly **49** involving two-step chemical transformations, as shown in Scheme 12.

It was subsequently used in olefin cross metathesis with 1-pentadecene in the presence of Grubbs' 2nd generation catalyst (5 mol%) to complete the synthesis of the title anticancer agent. At this stage, a number of trial experiments were conducted to increase the yield of cross metathesis product **50**. Thus, when 3 equivalents of 1-pentadecene were used in this reaction, **50** was obtained in 87% yield. In the next step, its benzyl deprotection and hydrogenation of the double bond were performed smoothly in the presence of H_2 atmosphere and 10% Pd/C in MeOH : CHCl_3 (2 : 1) to furnish Boc-protected amine **51** as a white solid in 91% yield. Its hydrolysis with a solution of dioxane saturated with HCl gas furnished the corresponding HCl salt of (+)-spisulosine (ES-285.HCl). Finally the title natural product (+)-spisulosine **52** (ES-285) was obtained in 90% yield by neutralizing the hydrochloride salt by aqueous NaOH (Scheme 12).

Conclusions

The present manuscript, dedicated to Professor S. K. Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday, focuses on syntheses of various types of biologically active marine natural products reported by my research group from time to time. The syntheses of all the title molecules were

successfully made possible by 'chiron approach', utilizing commercially available building blocks as chiral pool materials. While carbohydrate-based building blocks D-galactose and methyl α ,D-mannopyranoside were starting materials for the syntheses of jaspine B, antiepileptic ceramide and (+)-varitriol, L-serine-derived (*S*)-Garner's aldehyde was utilized as chiral pool material for the synthesis of (+)-spisulosine (ES-285). Our synthetic approach for the syntheses of all these cytotoxic natural products was very efficient where commercially available cheap reagents were used. Some of my students are currently involved in the synthesis of various analogues of these molecules, following the same synthetic protocols adopted for their synthesis discussed herein with a view to screen the analogues for their biological activities under CSIR-CDRI drug development programme.

Acknowledgement

The hard work dedicated by my students to complete the syntheses of above discussed marine natural products by 'chiron approach' is gratefully acknowledged. CDRI Communication number : 8510.

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